

REPORT

Psychometric Properties of the Persian Translation of Ely's L2 Tolerance of Ambiguity Scale

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Abstract

Tolerance of ambiguity (TA) is a well-researched affective construct in second language learning research. Numerous studies have examined the role of TA in learning foreign and second languages. Examining the role of TA in second language research necessitates the application of a valid and reliable scale to measure it. The only available scale to measure TA in second language contexts is Ely's second language tolerance of ambiguity scale. In this study, we translated this scale into Persian and examined its psychometric properties with the Rasch model. Findings revealed that the two reverse-scored items (Items 6 and 9) misfit the Rasch model and the 5-point Likert scale has disordered thresholds. When these two items were deleted and the middle category was merged with the adjacent category the data fitted the Rasch model. Therefore, we recommend a revised scale with a 4-point scale (omitting the 'neutral' category) and reworded Items 6 and 9 to be aligned with the other items (see Appendix).

Keywords: Ambiguity tolerance, validity, L2 tolerance of ambiguity scale, Rasch rating scale model

Introduction

Tolerance of ambiguity (TA) is a concept in personality psychology and individual differences that has gained a lot of attention over the past 70 years after its introduction by Frenkel-Brunswik (1948). TA has been studied in clinical psychology, medicine, organizational behavior, and second language learning. Frenkel-Brunswik (1949) defined TA as an "emotional and perceptual personality variable" and listed the behavioural characteristics of ambiguity intolerant people as "those with a tendency to resort to black-white solutions, to arrive at premature closure as to evaluative aspects, often at the neglect of reality, and to seek for unqualified and unambiguous over-all acceptance and rejection of other people."

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Budner (1962) defined TA as “the tendency to perceive ambiguous situations as desirable” and developed one of the first scales of TA. Ambiguity intolerant individuals have a tendency to resort to black-and-white solutions, have quick and overconfident judgment, often at the neglect of reality (Frenkel-Brunswik, 1949). Conversely, ambiguity tolerant individuals perceive ambiguous situations as desirable, challenging and interesting. TA correlates with Openness to Experience scale of the big-5 personality traits (Caligiuri, Jacobs, & Farr, 2000), with sensation-seeking and with risk-taking behaviour (McLain, 2009).

TA has been considered an important factor in second and foreign language learning. Ely (1989) states that language learning is full of uncertain situations. There are many instances where we do not know the meaning or the correct pronunciation or meaning of a word and this has motivated many researchers to try to determine to what extent second language learners are tolerant of ambiguity and how TA affects their process of second language learning. Perhaps the first study on TA and second language (L2) learning was conducted by Naiman, Frohlich, Stern, and Todesco (1978) who aimed to examine the predictors of language achievement among learners of French as a second language in Canada. Their research showed that those with higher TA are better in both receptive and productive language skills. Chapelle (1983) and Chapelle and Roberts (1986) demonstrated that TA correlates with TOEFL scores among ESL university students.

TA is often measured with a unidimensional scale. Naiman, et al. (1978) used Budner’s (1962) scale to measure TA and Chapelle (1983) and Chapelle and Roberts (1986) used Norton’s scale (1975) which are general TA scales and not specifically designed for second language contexts. Formerly, psychologists believed that cognitive styles and personality traits are stable across domains and contexts. However, Endler (1973) stated that this is not the case and these traits vary depending on the context in which they occur. Therefore, they should be operationalized specifically for each context. Durrheim and Foster (1997) argued that tolerance of ambiguity should not be assumed as a stable trait. They state that it varies from one domain to another. The level of ambiguity tolerance in one context is not necessarily the same as in another context.

The importance of the concept of TA in L2 and the lack of a specialized scale for L2 contexts led Ely (1989) to design the first TA scale for second language research. For this purpose, Ely (1989) defined TA in L2 contexts as “...the relative degree of discomfort associated with thinking: that one does not know or understand exact meaning; that one is not able to express one’s ideas accurately or exactly; that one is dealing with overly-complex language; that there is a lack of correspondence between the L1 and the L2” (p. 439). Ely’s scale contained 12 items on a 6-point Liker scale (from ‘strongly agree’ to ‘strongly disagree’). He reported that the items have acceptable item-total correlations with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.82. He further demonstrated that some of the items of an L2 strategies questionnaire significantly predict TA.

Over the past decades Ely's (1989, 1995) tolerance of ambiguity scale has become the standard TA scale in the L2 research. Numerous studies on the correlates of second and foreign language success have employed Ely's scale (Erten & Topkaya, 2009; Kimura, 2016; Soodmand Afshar & Khasemy, 2019). In the present study, Ely's (1989) tolerance of ambiguity scale was translated into Persian and validity evidence was provided using the Rasch model (Rasch, 1960/1980).

Method

Translation Procedure

The 12 items of the tolerance of ambiguity scale was translated into Persian by the authors (Appendix). In translation, great care was taken to express the same ideas and concepts in Persian without the interference of linguistic differences in the two languages. The Persian scale was revised and edited by colleagues and was back-translated from Persian into English by another colleague who had not seen the original English version. The original English and the back-translated versions were compared and discrepancies were resolved. The final Persian version was developed based on experts' comments and ideas derived from comparing the two English versions.

Participants

The participants of the study included 217 students of English as a foreign language in Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Tabaran University of Mashhad (only male participants) and Islamic Azad university of Mashhad, Iran. The data were collected in the context of a project on the impact of construct-irrelevant factors on reading comprehension tests in English as a second language (Ahmadjavaheri & Zeraatpishe, 2020). A 5-point Likert scale with 'Strongly Agree', 'Agree', 'Undecided', 'Disagree', and 'Strongly Disagree' was employed.

Data Analysis and Results

Validity evidence for the Persian translation of Ely's (1995) Second Language Tolerance of Ambiguity Scale was provided using the Rasch model (Rasch, 1960/1980). Rasch rating scale model (Andrich, 1978) was fitted to the 12 five-point Likert items of the scale. Winsteps Rasch measurement programme (Linacre, 2017a) was used for data analysis. Initial analysis of the data demonstrated that Item 6 with infit and outfit mean square values of 1.52 and 1.70, respectively and Item 9 with infit and outfit mean square values of 1.77 and 2.24, respectively misfit the model. The rest of the items had acceptable infit and outfit indices between 0.71 to 1.15. Principal components analysis (PCA) of standardized residuals showed that the eigenvalue in the first contrast is 2.1 which is slightly above the recommended value of 2 (Linacre, 2017b). Therefore, the data are not unidimensional and the Rasch model does not fit. The thresholds of the rating scale with values of -1.35, 0.20, -0.17, and 1.33 were also disordered. The disordering was in categories 2 and 3, which indicates that respondents cannot distinguish between these two categories. Person separation reliability was 0.80.

In the second step, the two misfitting items were deleted and categories 2 and 3 were merged. Reanalysis of the data showed that all the items fit the Rasch model. Table 1 shows the difficulty parameters, and infit and outfit values for the 10 remaining items in the scale. Person separation reliability increased to 0.84 after deleting the misfitting items.

Table 1: Item Parameters and Fit Values

ENTRY NUMBER	TOTAL SCORE	TOTAL COUNT	MEASURE	MODEL S.E.	INFIT		OUTFIT		PT-MEASURE		EXACT MATCH		ITEM
					MNSQ	ZSTD	MNSQ	ZSTD	CORR.	EXP.	OBS%	EXP%	
1	261	217	.53	.10	1.15	1.7	1.27	2.6	.56	.63	53.3	53.1	AT1
2	370	217	-.67	.11	.94	-.6	.98	-.2	.65	.63	63.1	58.2	AT2
3	263	217	.51	.10	.85	-1.7	.83	-1.9	.69	.63	57.9	53.1	AT3
4	260	217	.54	.10	.91	-1.0	.91	-1.0	.69	.63	56.5	53.1	AT4
5	260	217	.54	.10	1.02	.2	1.09	.9	.57	.63	50.5	53.1	AT5
6	DELETED												
7	347	217	-.41	.11	1.07	.8	1.07	.7	.60	.63	56.1	57.0	AT7
8	313	217	-.03	.10	.83	-2.0	.87	-1.4	.70	.63	64.5	55.7	AT8
9	DELETED												
10	367	217	-.64	.11	.74	-2.9	.72	-3.1	.71	.63	66.8	58.2	AT10
11	384	217	-.84	.11	.94	-.6	.95	-.5	.63	.63	58.9	59.0	AT11
12	267	217	.47	.10	1.47	4.7	1.51	4.8	.52	.63	47.7	54.1	AT12
MEAN	309.2	217.0	.00	.11	.99	-.1	1.02	.1			57.5	55.5	
S.D.	50.2	.0	.55	.00	.20	2.1	.22	2.2			5.8	2.3	

The PCA of residuals showed that the eigenvalue in the first contrast is 1.70 which is lower than 2. This supports unidimensionality and the fit of data to the Rasch model. After merging categories 2 and 3 the thresholds became ordered with values of -1.92, -0.49, and 2.40. Figure 1 shows the category probability curves for the scale. As the figure shows all the categories have a peak for a certain portion of the scale and are completely ordered.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of item thresholds and person parameters. Each "#" is two persons and each "." is one person. As the maps shows, the item thresholds fully cover the distribution of person parameters. That is, the scale covers the entire range of the levels of ambiguity tolerance and works optimally for measuring all the levels of the trait continuum.

Figure 1: Category Probability Curves for the Scale

Figure 2: Wright Map of the Distribution Persons and Items with Thresholds

Conclusion

Language learning, whether in the classroom or individually, is full of ambiguities. Deficiencies in both linguistic and L2 cultural knowledge lead to ambiguous situations. Ambiguity may result in anxiety (Oxford, 1999) which could impede the progress of L2 learning (White, 1999). The study of AT and its impact on L2 learning has attracted the attention of many researcher over the past four decades. Researchers have demonstrated that AT affects the process of second language learning and is associated with L2 strategy use (Nishimo, 2007; Oxford, 1999). The importance of AT in L2 research necessitates the construction of valid and reliable scales to measure this construct. Early research on AT relied on general AT measures from psychology but in the late 1980's Ely developed a 12-item scale to be used specifically in L2 contexts. To our knowledge, this is the only AT scale developed for L2 contexts to date.

In this study, we translated Ely's (1989) scale into Persian via forward and backward translation procedure. The scale was revised based on the translations discrepancies and colleagues' comments. The scale was assigned to a sample of Iranian undergraduate students of English as a foreign language. Rasch rating scale model was used to provide validity evidence for the scale. Fit of a latent trait model like the Rasch model is evidence that the covariation underlying the responses are caused by a common latent trait and fit of the items show that as levels of the latent trait increases the probability of getting a higher score also increases too (Baghaei & Tabatabaee-Yazdi, 2016; Baghaei & Shoahosseini, 2019).

Findings showed that two items (Item 6 and Item 9) misfit the Rasch model. These two items are the only items which needed reverse scoring due to negative orientation of their scales. Previous research has shown that reverse-scored items create problems and result in the formation of spurious dimensions (Moradi, 2020). When item 6 and 9 were deleted the data fit the Rasch model and PCA of standardized residuals indicated unidimensionality. Furthermore, evaluation of item-person map showed that the scale well targets the respondents.

Analysis of rating scale response categories showed that the threshold parameters were disordered. Therefore, the categories 2 and 3 were collapsed a 4-point Likert scale was developed. This resulted in better psychometric properties for the instrument. Previous studies have demonstrated that the middle category of 'neutral' or 'undecided' usually misfit the Rasch model (Baghaei, Hohensinn & Kubinger, 2014; Baghaei, & Cassady, 2014; Shoahosseini & Baghaei, 2020). The reason probably is that endorsing the middle category does not indicate a progression on the latent dimension but in data analysis we assume it does. In other words, 'neutral' does not indicate a higher level of the latent trait than 'disagree', and 'strongly disagree'. It simply means that the respondent does not have any idea. But in data analysis we score it as if it means more than the categories below it. Future research should evaluate the scale with four response categories and with Items 6 and 9 revised to be aligned with the other items. In the Persian scale in the Appendix, we deleted the middle category of 'neutral' and reworded Items 6 and 9

to be aligned with the other items. We recommend this form of the scale to be used both in Persian and English.

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پرسشنامه تحمل ابهام الی (1995)

دانشجویان گرامی: پرسشنامه زیر برای اندازه گیری میزان تحمل ابهام شما طراحی شده است. خواهشمند است میزان درستی هریک از جملات را درمورد خود با صداقت مشخص نمایید. از همکاری شما صمیمانه سپاسگزاریم. پاسخهای شما کاملا محرمانه باقی می ماند.

جنسیت : مرد زن
 رشته تحصیلی :
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 سن :
 معدل ترم گذشته:.....

ردیف	عنوان	کاملا موافقم	موافقم	مخالقم	کاملا مخالفم
1	وقتی به زبان انگلیسی می خوانم، اگر متوجه معنی نشوم، بی حوصله میشوم.				
2	اگر متوجه نشوم معلم به انگلیسی دقیقا چه می گوید ناراحت می شوم، حتی اگر منظور کلی را بفهمم.				
3	از اینکه نمی توانم ایده هایم را با جزئیات و روشن به انگلیسی بنویسم ناراحتم.				
4	از اینکه گاهی اوقات معنی ساختارهای دستوری زبان انگلیسی را نمی فهمم ناراحت می شوم.				
5	از اینکه ممکن است تلفظ انگلیسی من درست نباشد حس خوبی ندارم.				
6	خواندن متون انگلیسی که قدری زمان می برند(چالشی هستند) تا بطور کامل درک شوند را دوست ندارم.				
7	از اینکه حتی با خواندن زیاد دستور زبان انگلیسی باز هم هنوز برایم دشوار است، ناراحتم.				
8	از اینکه وقتی به انگلیسی می نویسم، نمی توانم آنچه را که می خواهم بگویم، ناراحتم.				
9	وقتی به انگلیسی حرف می زنم از اینکه نمی توانم آنچه را که می خواهم بگویم ناراحت هستم.				
10	وقتی معلم یک کلمه انگلیسی استفاده می کند که من نمی دانم ناراحت می شوم.				
11	از اینکه گاهی تقریبا غیر ممکن است که برای کلمات انگلیسی معادل فارسی پیدا کرد ناراحتم.				
12	کاش میتوانستم کلمات انگلیسی را درست تلفظ نمایم.				